

RESPONSE PAPER**LAST NAME: ABDELGADIR****FIRST NAME: GAWAHIR****PROGRAM CODE: DIPH****COURSE CODE: ACA-401D****PERIOD NUMBER: 6****INSTRUCTOR: DR GULMA****Edit or delete text to show the actual information below:**

The author applied US conventions of grammar, usage, and mechanics

The student must use Turabian/Chicago parenthetical/in-text references (ideally with Zotero) and confirm below:

The author did use Zotero to insert references

The author did use Grammarly Premium (provided by EUCLID)

My plagiarism rate (per Grammarly Premium) is: 2 %

The author used the following software: (MSWord 2016 on Windows 11)

QUIZ FOR COURSE ACA-401D

1. One of the basic citation forms is:

- Paranthetical citation.¹**
- Credibility.
- Boost efficiency.
- A semicolon form.

2. What is the recommended way to format a book title in a bibliography entry?

- In all capital letters, with no italics.
- In sentence case, with the first word and proper nouns capitalized.

¹ Kate L. Turabian, *A Manual for Writers of Research Papers, Theses, and Dissertations: Chicago Style for Students and Researchers*, eighth edition (Chicago: University of Chicago Press, 2013), 142.

- In the title case, with the main title and any subtitle in italic font.²**
- In all lowercase letters, with no italics.
3. The following situations require citations, except:
- When you quote exact words from an exact source.
- When you paraphrase ideas that are associated with a specific source.
- When you use any ideas, data, or methods attributable to any source you consulted.
- Author, title, and facts of publication.³**
4. What are some examples of paraphrasing in academic writing?
- These are the exact words of an author.
- Are the ideas and information the author has produced on a topic but written in your own words.⁴**
- Are the publication information for each of the sources that were cited in the Paper.
- Are when the writer uses a source of information without crediting the author of that source of information.

²Turabian, Kate L. *et al.*, 692.

³Ibid., 136–37.

⁴Laurent Cleenewerck and Kabiru Gulma. *ACA-401/ACA-401D Coursepack: Period 1*, Fifth Edition (Washington, D.C.: Euclid University Press, 2024), 40.

5. What is the correct format for citing a journal article with multiple authors in a WHO publication, according to the WHO Editorial Style Manual?
- List all authors, separated by commas, followed by the year of publication.
 - List the first three authors, followed by "et al." and the year of publication.**⁵
 - List only the first author, followed by the year of publication.
 - List all authors, separated by semicolons, followed by the year of publication.
6. According to the WHO Editorial Style Manual, what font is recommended for WHO publications?
- Arial
 - Calibri
 - times New Roman.**⁶
 - Verdana

⁵ World Health Organization. *WHO Style Guide. Second Edition.* (Geneva: World Health Organization, 2013), 39.

⁶ *Ibid.*, 32.

7. How should abbreviations be presented in a European-style reference list, according to the European Commission's English Style Guide?
- In full, followed by the acronym in parentheses.**⁷
 - Only the abbreviation, without explanation.
 - In the title case, without punctuation.
 - In all capital letters, with punctuation.
8. What is the recommended way to format a reference list entry for a book with one author, according to the European style?
- Title, author's last name, first name, year of publication, publisher.
 - Author's last name, first name, title, publisher, year of publication.
 - Author's last name, title, first name, year of publication, publisher.
 - Author's last name, first name, year of publication. title, publisher.**⁸

⁷ European Commission, *English Style Guide: A Handbook for Authors and Translators in the European Commission*, January 2016, 24–25.

⁸ *Ibid.*, 29.

9. Which of the following research methods is typically associated with qualitative research?
- Surveys with multiple-choice questions.
 - Experiments with control groups.
 - In-depth interviews with open-ended questions.**⁹
 - Observational studies with statistical analysis.
10. What is the primary goal of qualitative research, as opposed to quantitative research?
- To test hypotheses and predict outcomes using statistical methods.
 - To explore and understand phenomena through in-depth analysis and interpretation.**¹⁰
 - To measure variables and identify correlations using numerical data.
 - To generalize findings to a larger population using random sampling.

⁹ Sampson, James P., *A Guide to Quantitative and Qualitative Dissertation Research*. Second Edition (Routledge: Florida State University, March 24, 2017), 30.

¹⁰ Ibid., 42.

BIBLIOGRAPHY

- Cleenewerck, Laurent and Kabiru Gulma. *ACA -401D Coursepack: Period 1*. Fifth Edition. Bangui: Euclid University, 2024.
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Cleenewerck, Laurent and Kabiru Abubakar Gulma. 2025. ACA-401/ACA 401D Course Pack: Period 1. 6th ed. Washington, D.C.: Euclid University Press. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15245536>.